

THE CONTENT OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN DEVELOPING IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY AMONG STUDENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF AN INFORMATION SOCIETY

O.R.Ortikov

Associate Professor of the Department of Pedagogy,
Bukhara State University

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
o.r.ortikov@buxdu.uz

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1977-7632>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17947187>

Abstract: In the context of an information society, developing ideological immunity among university students is one of the pressing pedagogical challenges. Spiritual and educational activities serve as a key mechanism for fostering students' critical thinking, commitment to national and universal values, civic responsibility, and conscious attitude toward alien and destructive ideas. The article highlights the content and methods of organizing spiritual and educational activities in higher education institutions aimed at strengthening the ideological stability of youth in an information-rich environment.

Keywords: spiritual and educational activities, ideological immunity, university students, higher education institutions, national and universal values, critical thinking, civic responsibility, information culture, resistance to alien ideas.

Аннотация: В условиях информационного общества формирование идеологического иммунитета у студентов является одной из актуальных педагогических задач. Духовно-просветительская деятельность выступает ключевым механизмом, способствующим развитию у студентов критического мышления, приверженности национальным и универсальным ценностям, гражданской ответственности и осознанного отношения к чуждым и деструктивным идеям. Статья раскрывает содержание и методы организации духовно-просветительской работы в высших учебных заведениях, направленные на укрепление идеологической устойчивости молодежи в информационно-насыщенной среде.

Ключевые слова: духовно-просветительская деятельность, идеологический иммунитет, студенты, высшие учебные заведения, национальные и универсальные ценности, критическое мышление, гражданская ответственность, информационная культура, противодействие чуждым идеям.

In our country, special attention is being paid to the development of science and spirituality, as well as to large-scale creative and constructive activities. State

youth policy is aimed at ensuring that young people develop on the basis of national and universal values. In this study, educating students as specialists who possess a conscious attitude toward information, critical thinking skills, and a well-formed personal position is identified as an important objective. In this regard, the development of such qualities as independent and critical thinking and creativity based on axiological, cognitive, activity-oriented, and integrative approaches is of particular relevance.

It is important to plan spiritual and educational activities in higher education institutions, to develop students' thinking and cognitive activity, and to apply theoretical knowledge in practice [4]. Ensuring the consistency and effectiveness of planned activities and implementing spiritual and educational work in cooperation with teachers are essential. These efforts contribute to the formation of ideological immunity among young people and help protect them from various risks in the era of globalization.

In our country, it is of great importance to organize the educational process in the system of continuous education in harmony with upbringing and spiritual-educational activities. Taking into account the didactic significance of effectively organizing the teaching-learning process on the basis of modern pedagogical approaches, a number of pedagogical scholars have conducted research aimed at the widespread use of innovative technologies in the development of spiritual and educational activities. In this regard, the scientific works, textbooks and teaching manuals, scientific articles and monographs of pedagogical researchers such as V. P. Bepalko, I. Ya. Lerner, B. T. Likhachev, M. V. Klarin, Ye. S. Polat, N. Saidakhmedov, O'. Tolipov, M. Ochilov, N. Azizxo'jaeva, B. Farberman, K. Zaripov, J. Yo'ldoshev, O. Roziqov, B. Adizov, B. Xodjaev, Sh. Olimov, K. Usmonov and S. Og'aev were studied.

Among scholars of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), N. K. Baranov, S. V. Kun'shikov, P. V. Kolozaridi, T. I. Oyzerman, E. N. Chekushkina, M. A. Kovalyov, E. B. Boev and M. Turovskaya thoroughly examined issues related to ideology and ideological immunity in their scientific research.

Foreign pedagogical and psychological scholars such as V. Druzin, I. Kolotilova, O. Petrich, A. Rean, R. Cialdini and others attempted to scientifically analyze ideological struggles, ideological threats facing students, manipulation processes, mass culture and its manifestations, as well as various forms of ideological confrontation. In the scientific studies of A. Destutt de Tracy, Slavoj Žižek, George Wolford, Harold Walsby, Charles Blattberg, David Minar and Willard Mullins, the theoretical and practical aspects of ideology and ideological

immunity, along with their philosophical, socio-political and educational characteristics, are comprehensively explored.

Our analysis of the issues related to “the development of ideological immunity among students in the process of spiritual and educational activities, based on idea-generation technologies, scientific and methodological foundations, pedagogical and psychological characteristics, and ways of improvement” [3] was conducted on the basis of observations, empirical experiences, and an analysis of scholarly literature.

This process requires the formulation of scientific conclusions that reveal the essence of the topic, as well as the theoretical interpretation and classification of key concepts such as spirituality, enlightenment, ideology, immunity, and ideological immunity. Based on the sources studied and observations carried out during the research, it was determined that the didactic structure of developing students’ ideological immunity serves to strengthen cooperation among social institutions, including educational institutions, the family, the neighborhood (mahalla), and the wider community.

Furthermore, the necessity of analyzing national customs and traditions, the historical and conceptual interpretation of education, and the system of universal human relations within a historical context, as well as aligning the content of pedagogical approaches with educational objectives, requires providing clear and scientific definitions of the key terms of the study. Therefore, special attention was given to the following concepts within the framework of the research.

“Spirituality” is a complex socio-psychological phenomenon that reflects an individual’s behavior, inner world, and attitude toward values and traditions. In a broad sense, spirituality encompasses the internal moral standards, beliefs, ethical norms, cultural awareness, and intellectual development of both the individual and society. According to explanatory dictionaries, the term *spirituality* derives from the Arabic word “*ma’na*” (معنى), meaning “content,” “inner essence,” and “spiritual value.”

“Immunity” (Latin: *immunitas, immunitatus* — liberation, protection) [6, p. 202] refers to the ability of the organism to protect itself against foreign and harmful factors, particularly microorganisms and toxic substances. It is an essential mechanism for maintaining the biological integrity and stability of the organism.

Thus, immunity represents the natural and acquired defense system that protects the organism from infections (viruses, bacteria, fungi), toxins, and other harmful influences. The strength of immunity is closely related to adherence to a

healthy lifestyle, balanced nutrition, physical activity, and psychological stability [6, p. 202].

The interpretation of this biological concept within a socio-pedagogical context forms the basis for the concept of “ideological immunity.”

“Ideological immunity” is the ability of an individual to demonstrate a conscious, critical, and stable attitude toward alien, destructive, and manipulative ideas. It is characterized by independent thinking, commitment to national and universal values, a culture of selective information consumption, and the formation of internal protective mechanisms against ideological threats.

From a pedagogical perspective, ideological immunity is formed gradually through the development of students’ critical thinking, social responsibility, civic engagement, and information literacy. In this process, the systematic organization of spiritual and educational activities, along with the use of innovative technologies and modern pedagogical approaches, plays a crucial role.

Scientific and analytical studies conducted indicate that spiritual and educational activities play an invaluable role in developing ideological immunity among university students. Through such activities, students develop commitment to national and universal values, critical thinking skills, civic responsibility, and a conscious attitude toward alien and destructive ideas.

Based on the research findings, it was determined that the systematic and effective organization of spiritual and educational work in higher education institutions serves as an important pedagogical mechanism for ensuring students’ ideological stability. Especially in the context of the modern information environment and global processes, spiritual and educational activities act as an effective means of enhancing students’ ideological independence, increasing their social engagement, and strengthening their immunity against ideological threats.

Therefore, by enriching spiritual and educational activities with innovative formats, interactive methods, and modern technologies, it is possible to foster students’ ideological immunity and ensure their stable and responsible personal development. This process not only enhances the pedagogical capacity of higher education institutions but also contributes to the formation of a stable ideological environment within society.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5040 “On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the System of Spiritual and Educational Work,” March 26, 2021.

2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.” // Xalq so‘zi, October 9, 2019.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4307 dated May 3, 2019 “On Additional Measures to Improve the Effectiveness of Spiritual and Educational Work.” // Xalq so‘zi, May 4, 2019.
4. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Humanity, Goodness, and Creativity – the Foundation of Our National Idea. Tashkent: Tasvir Publishing House, 2021. – 36 p.
5. Nichkalo N. G., Filonova G. N., Suhodolskaya-Kuleshova O. V. Modern Education as an Open System. Moscow: Institute of Scientific and Pedagogical Information of the Russian Academy of Education, “UNITY-DANA” Publishing, “YURKOMPANY” Publishing, 2012. – 576 p.
6. Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language. Volume Two. Tashkent: State Scientific Publishing House of the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2020. – 202 p.
7. Ortiqov O. R. Using the Work Qabusnoma in Shaping Students’ Moral and Ethical Qualities // Sonferensea, 2023. – P. 1–5.
8. Ortiqov O. R. Technologies for Developing Ideological Immunity in the Process of Spiritual and Educational Work (on the Example of Higher Education Institutions) // Ekonomika i Sotsium, 2022. – № 3-2 (94). – P. 1130–1135.
9. Olimov S., Artikov O., Murodova M. The Use of National Values in Forming the Ecological Worldview of Students // BIO Web of Conferences. EDP Sciences, 2024. – Vol. 141. – P. 04027.
10. Murodova M. M. Pedagogical Deontology and Competence in the Activity of Future Primary School Teachers // Scientific Progress, 2022. – Vol. 3, № 1. – P. 90–97.